

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) chromosome 6D harbours the broad spectrum common bunt resistance gene *Bt11*

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(a) MP-PR1

Lunzer, M., Buerstmayr, M., Grausgruber, H., Müllner, A.E., Fallbacher, I. and Buerstmayr, H. Theoretical and Applied Genetics.

(b) MP-PR2

(c) MP-PL

(d) MP-MM

Supplementary File 7: Boxplots showing common bunt incidence (CBI) levels in percent for recombinant inbred lines (RILs) harbouring resistance conferring alleles for different QTL(-combinations). Results are shown for all four mapping populations (MPs) individually: (a) 'Rainer' \times PI 166910 (b) PI 166910 \times 'Rainer' (c) PI 166910 \times 'Lukulus' (d) M822123 \times 'Mulan'. Orange squares mark average CBI, green dots indicate outliers. The number of RILs harbouring the respective QTL(-combinations) is given on the x-axis